

Employee Discipline Management and Organizational Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Ondo Town, Ondo State

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluates the relationship between employee discipline management (EDM) and organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state. Four (4) variables of employee discipline management were examined, disciplinary procedure, disciplinary actions, disciplinary policies and disciplinary codes in relationship with the dependent variable organizational performance. Descriptive survey research design was used for this study with population of 233 using stratified random probability technique and a sampling size of 145 while 134 respondent's questionnaire were retrieved for analysis. From the result of the analysis carried out using Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS), it was discovered that Disciplinary Actions (DC) and Disciplinary Policies (DPO) were positively and significantly related to Organizational Performance (OP) while, Disciplinary Procedure (DP) shows a positive but insignificant relationship with organizational performance (OP) and Disciplinary Codes (DC) was negatively and insignificantly related with Organizational Performance (OP) of DMBs in Ondo town, Ondo state. The study concludes that disciplinary procedures should be looked into by management on how best this practice would impact on organizational performance. Thus, it was recommended and suggested that further study should be undertaken to evaluate other disciplinary measures of employee discipline management and Organizations especially DMBs should incorporate disciplinary procedure as it aims to promote fairness and procedural justice in dealing with employee discipline. The advantages for organizations of a consistent disciplinary procedure are threefold, these include the fact that it contributes to the stability of the workforce, labour turnover is minimized, and it promotes organizational performance.

Keywords: Employee discipline management, Disciplinary Actions, Disciplinary Codes, Disciplinary Procedures, Disciplinary Policies and Organizational Performance

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INTRODUCTION

The first structured introduction of discipline into organizations was established in the United States of America in the 1930s in response to the trade unions' request to eliminate summary terminations. It is in this place a progressive system of punishment was developed. It was envisaged that this process would provide a worker with protection against loss of job (Agbo, 2020). Shilumani (2020) states that in both developed and developing countries, a range of legislative instruments or interventions is recognized to regulate the nature of employer and employee relations in the prevention of disruptive labour practices whose consequences could be harmful to socio-economic development (Haji & Syahidin, 2022). According to Choudharyi and Rana (2022), organizations are constituted of individuals and groups of individuals who work interdependently and collectively to ensure organizational goals. Thus, employee discipline is a strategy or system used by employers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change their behaviour and as an effort to increase their awareness and willingness to comply with all company regulations and applicable norms (Dauda & Katamba, 2022). Furthermore, employees are the lifeblood of an organization and it is expected that their conduct must be in tandem with the rules and policies of their organization. Discipline is the most important for a healthy atmosphere, sustainable growth of Industry, and for the achievement of organizational goals (Dauda & Katamba, 2022). It is against this background that this study evaluates employee discipline management and organizational performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Ondo town, Ondo state.

Based on the existing empirical studies show that most researchers dealt more with employee or work discipline on employee's performance, employees commitment, job satisfaction and sustainability (Sarwari, 2016; Ignatius & Ruliyanto, 2017; Tinovitasari, *et al.*, 2017; Cerdayana, *et al.*, 2018; Tantau & Wopara, 2019; Nduka, *et al.*, 2019; Iskamto, *et al.*, 2020; Surajiyo, *et al.*, 2021; Muhammad, *et al.*, 2021; and Dauda & Katamba, 2022; Haji & Sychidin, 2022;) and they were able to reveal how staff discipline influence their performances. Furthermore, previous studies show that not much research has been conducted in Nigeria, unlike other developed countries as regards employee discipline management and organizational performance. Thus, this study evaluates employee discipline management and organizational performance.

Other studies carried out in Nigeria used Government parastatals such as hospitals, schools, and local government amongst others as their case studies and the components of measuring employee discipline management were leadership style, organizational culture, training, working environment, level of performance amongst others in evaluating employee discipline management such as (Okwudili & Ugwuerue 2015; Iheanacho, *et al.*, 2017; Ubah, *et al.*, 2019; Dauda & Katamba, 2022) amongst others thereby not looking at the main components that affect employee discipline management. Only a few studies were able to evaluate employee discipline management using corrective measures (Nwinyokpugi 2015; Idris & Alegbeleye 2015; Mbinya, 2017; Maimuna 2018; Kogah & Ibegbulem 2021). Other developed countries carried out similar research (Knight & Ukpere, 2014; Marsela 2017; Tantau & Wopara, 2019; Kogah & Ibegbulem, 2021; Chew &

Taylor, 2021; Sishi 2022). Agbo 2020 evaluated employee discipline management using preventive measures which consist of disciplinary actions, disciplinary procedures, disciplinary policies and the code of conduct or disciplinary code. Since no similar study has been carried out in Nigeria using preventive measures, which reveals a knowledge gap. Thus, the study filled this gap by evaluating employee's discipline management and organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state.

Based on the statement of the problem, this study evaluates the following research questions.

- i. What is the impact of disciplinary procedures on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state?
- ii. How do disciplinary actions influence the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state?
- iii. Do disciplinary policies impact the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state?
- iv. What is the influence of disciplinary codes on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state?

The following hypotheses were formulated to provide answers to the research question derived from the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of disciplinary procedures on the organization performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of disciplinary actions on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state.

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of disciplinary policies on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state.

H₀₄: There is no significant influence of disciplinary codes on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state.

The study evaluates employee discipline management and organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state. This was selected based on the accessibility of financial resources and the collection of data. Four major elements were used for this study in evaluating employee discipline management (disciplinary procedures, disciplinary actions, disciplinary policies, disciplinary codes) which serves as the independent variable while the dependent variable is organizational performance. The population is made up of the core and non-core staff of Access bank, Eco bank, First Bank of Nigeria Limited, Heritage bank, Polaris bank and Wema bank located in Ondo town, Ondo State. The total population was 233 using stratified random probability technique and a sampling size of 145. Descriptive survey research design was used for this study while Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS) was used to analyze the data. The timeframe for the study was between January to July, 2023.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Performance

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Tran *et al.* (2020) posited that organizational performance is improved by emphasizing the important roles of innovation, organizational learning and transformational leadership. Nevertheless, the role of employee willingness to perform contributes to increased levels of performance and those employees who are more willing to perform, contribute more significantly to organizational success (Raza, *et al.*, 2020). The level of organizational performance is determined by various contributing factors that include operational efficiencies, mergers, acquisitions and levels of diversification, organizational structures, top management team composition and style, human resource management, manipulation of the political and/or social influences intruding upon the market conformity (Haque, 2020). Thus, it is the extent to which an organization meets its objectives and can be determined by assessing its financial and non-financial indicators against the set goals (Garavan, *et al.*, 2021). Also, it is a multi-dimensional construct that is influenced by different factors that are both internal and external (Meshari, *et al.* 2021; Zamhir, *et al.* 2022).

Employee's Discipline Management

Nduka, *et al.* (2019) defined employee discipline management as the personal efforts at self-control to adhere to the stated procedures and regulations of an organization to ensure that organizational goals are achieved (Agbo, 2020). Though employee discipline management is useful in educating employees to comply with and enjoy existing regulations, procedures, and policies so that they can produce a good performance, in a disciplined environment, a company will be able to accomplish its programs and the goals that have been arranged where a good leader must strive so that his subordinates have good discipline and must also set an example in carrying out good discipline in an organization (Madiistriyatno & Kamsinah, 2022). Therefore, it can be concluded that employee discipline management in an organization is needed to smooth all existing affairs. For example, an errand boy in an office arrives late, and as a result, all of the workrooms in the office are locked, so that the office's activities are disrupted, because there are no employees who can carry out their activities, thus disrupting the operation process that day (Haji & Syahidin, 2022).

Disciplinary Procedure

Thierry (2018) opined that disciplinary procedures are used to correct behaviour which contradicts organizational goals and bring about labour peace in the workplace. but, if incorrectly applied, its consequences can be felt throughout the organization since the performance of any organization depends on the commitment and determination of its human capital to make both employers and employees committed to each other and the progress of the organization. Companies designed disciplinary procedures to harness, enhance and encourage all employees to cultivate and maintain standards of conduct, attendance and job performance and some of these procedures are being made available to employees in employee handbooks whilst others are being displayed in the offices of such organizations. In the ideal situation, they should apply to all employees and must be consistent and fair to all in the organization (Agbo, 2020). Moreover, some staff members indulge in the practice of absenteeism and presenteeism *which* are a breach of disciplinary procedures and non-adherence to the *code of ethics* in the workplace, which later affects the efficiency and quality of service delivery (Chewe & Taylor, 2021). Thus, Employers need to ensure

that disciplinary procedures are fully utilized to ensure that any dismissal is considered 'fair', both in a legal and moral sense (Choudhary & Rana, 2022).

Disciplinary Actions

While disciplining an employee, it is always important to make sure that the disciplinary action meted out to the offender is always commensurate to the offence committed. It is important to mete out the same punishment to the same category of offenders (Aparia, 2017). And another vital thing in punishing offenders is that the person must be allowed to be heard. He or she must explain the reasons for his or her action before a decision is taken against him or her and certain mild offences should also be punished with mild penalties (Maimuna, 2018). Disciplinary actions may have serious repercussions on the employees, organizations and even on the organization, they must be based on certain principles to be fair and acceptable to the employees, their representatives and other interested parties (Nduka, *et al.* 2019). Thus, proper employee discipline is very important for promoting fairness and order in the treatment of individuals and the conduct of labour-management relations (Choudhary & Rana, 2022).

Disciplinary Policies

Bodo (2018) argued that reported cases were reviewed to establish how many related to disciplinary issues where two out of twenty-seven reported cases related to disciplinary issues and it also, found that for a disciplinary process to be acceptable in an organization, should be documented and seen to be applied fairly and what constitutes offences should be clear and the process should be applied fairly with an appeal process in place. Marlow, *et al.* (2018) found that all organisations rely on proper communication of policies and procedures for their basic functioning as communication is used to transfer organisational rules, regulations, policies and procedures to employees. Nduka, *et al.* (2019) stated that the adoption of a divide-and-rule policy generates resentment, misunderstanding, and division among employees which causes serious issues to an organizational goal. Thus, proper communication of organisational policies enhances good relationships and minimises issues in an organization between the employer and employee (Musheke & Phiri, 2021).

Disciplinary Codes

Shilumani (2020) argued that a disciplinary code is a guide or means for employees to know and understand what performance or behavioural traits are required of them. And failing to establish rules and regulations in an organisation is a challenge which allows an employee to behave recklessly in any way they like. The absence of organisational rules and regulations and a code of conduct affect workplace discipline. Dheviests and Riyanto (2020) contended that most organisational rules on the books cannot elicit compliance to achieve their objectives. Organisational rules and regulations must be understood in the context in which they operate to improve compliance. Codes of conduct that are ineffective in meeting its goals are just as damaging to the organisation and may not be effective in ensuring discipline in an organisation (Doellgast & Benassi, 2020). disciplinary code of an organization assented to by staff it can be applied whether the employee gives his or her consent or not. Though, whether the process is regarded as unfair, alternatives are usually made in the disciplinary code for challenges (Kogah & Ibegbulem, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

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Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework of the Study (Researchers Conceptualization, 2023)

Theoretical Review

Resource-Based View Theory

As the follow-up on the theory of the growth of a firm which was introduced by Penrose (1959), the resource-based theory was later developed and expatriated by Wernerfelt (1984). The resource-based view theory (RBV) has been used in the studies of organizational performance and it focuses on the unique resources that the organization has and capabilities that differentiate the organization from its competitors in a similar industry (Tate & Bals, 2018). Miller (2019) opined that resource-based view theory gives an insight into how organizations can achieve a competitive advantage over other organizations and improve their organizational performance. These resources and capabilities enhance organizational performance and enable an organization to obtain a competitive advantage. According to Okpiabhele and Tafamel (2020), this theory deals with the firm characteristics internally and their effects on performance. It was based on the assumptions like other theories where some of these assumptions directly affect the superior or employer of the company performance theories. It focuses on the measurement of superior performance for evaluating the competitiveness of an organization

Reinforcement Theory

According to Asadullah et al. (2019), the theory was developed by Skinner. As a behavioural paradigm, the reinforcement theory is derived from the work of behavioural psychologist, B.F Skinner and it is based on the notion that rewarded behaviours are more likely to be repeated, while punishable behaviours are eliminated. Also, the theory states that reinforcements play a vital role in ensuring that desired behaviour is produced and it is applied in organizational settings since its discovery in 1969 to minimize the occurrence of undesirable behaviour and improve desirable behaviour (Sishi, 2022). In an organizational setting, contingency managers can either withhold

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rewards or give a reinforcement, guided by employee behaviour. Kelly and Pohl (2018) stated that the reinforcement theory makes use of the terms such as operant behaviour, reinforcing stimuli, schedules of reinforcement, successive approximations and positive and negative reinforcement. In relating this theory with this study, it is believed that using reinforcement effectively should make punishment unnecessary and that using non-reinforcement is the most effective strategy for weakening bad behaviour (Asadullah, *et al.*, 2019; Moergen, *et al.*, 2020). Unluckily, managers may view punishment as an effective strategy to deal with an employee's future aggressive behaviour and this notion implies that managers who have been subjected to punishment as ordinary employees may also prefer to use punishment (Sishi, 2022).

Empirical Review

Maimuna (2018) conducted the impact of employee discipline on organizational performance with specific reference to NIDI Industry Limited. It was based heavily on observation, interviews, textbooks, journal articles, magazines and newspapers for reviews and findings. It was able to discover that discipline has a positive impact on employee performance. It was also discovered that employee discipline is an integral aspect of the organization system and the real purpose of discipline is to encourage employees to meet standards of job performance and to behave sensibly and safely at work, rather than to punish.

Nduka *et al.*, (2019) examined the relationship between workplace discipline and organizational effectiveness of Abia State Polytechnic, Aba. It was revealed that unfair management practices, lack of adequate supervision of employees and nepotism about critical issues are the major causes of indiscipline among the staff of Abia State Polytechnic. Also, the study revealed that the common disciplinary measures used to address indiscipline are oral reprimand, issuance of a query letter and dismissal. Furthermore, it was found that the enforcement of sanctions and penalties on violators, responsive and sound leadership and giving attention to employees' needs and grievances are the most effective ways of maintaining discipline in Abia.

Ubah, *et al.* (2019) focused on discipline and organizational performance in Nigeria. The ethical theory was used to analyze the topic. The study made use of a secondary source of data through a literature review approach. The result showed that the effect of discipline on organizational performance includes industrial peace and harmony, increased revenue, employee career development, environment friendliness as well as organizational high productivity. Also, it was discovered that socio-cultural, political, managerial and economic factors are responsible for employee discipline in Nigerian organizations.

Tantua and Wopara (2019) examined the relationship between disciplinary tools and employee commitment of construction firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Primary data was collated through a self-administered, structured questionnaire. It was revealed from the findings that there is a negative and significant relationship between disciplinary tools and employee commitment of construction firms in Rivers State. Also, findings revealed that all the dimensions of disciplinary tools and employee commitment were negatively correlated.

Agbo (2020) examined the effect of employees' discipline on the organizational performance of Nigerian Breweries Plc. Enugu, Enugu State. Descriptive statistics were employed to analyse the demographic characteristics of respondents. The findings showed that taking all other independent

variables at zero, the code of discipline was 0.577 and disciplinary procedures show 0.157 while discipline systems show 0.082 and disciplinary actions was 0.021 increase in the scores of the employee performance. This inferred that code of discipline influenced the employee performance most, followed by discipline systems, disciplinary procedures and then disciplinary actions.

Kogah and Ibegbulem (2021) examined the influence of query and demotion as disciplinary measures on librarians' job performance in university libraries in South East, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design while the instrument for data collection was a rating scale. Data collected were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions while a t-test was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. The result shows that the query as a disciplinary measure has a significant influence on the job performance of librarians while demotion has a very low negative and non-significant influence on the job performance of librarians.

Dauda and Katamba (2022) highlighted the influence of work discipline and job satisfaction on the job performance of medical records managers in federal medical centres in North-Central, Nigeria. The study was guided by five corresponding research questions and three null hypotheses. A survey research design method was adopted and the target population of 376 medical record managers in five federal medical centres in North-Central, Nigeria was used for the study. It was concluded from the study that variables which improve the level of job satisfaction of medical record managers should be looked into such as remuneration, leadership style, working environment and policy, training and development of members of staff for effective output.

Chewe and Taylor (2021) examined the relationship between disciplinary procedures, employee punctuality and employee performance. From the result, disciplinary procedures positively affect employee performance; disciplinary procedures positively affect employee punctuality; employee punctuality positively affects employee performance; disciplinary procedures and employee performance were moderated by employee punctuality were tested. From the hypothesis tested, disciplinary procedures positively affect employee performance was supported.

Choudhary and Rana (2022) examined the enforcement of sanctions and penalties on violators, responsive and sound leadership and giving attention to employees' needs and grievances are the most effective ways of maintaining discipline in any organization. The study recommends that management should attend swiftly to the yearnings and grievances of its staff.

Sishi (2022) investigated the impact of workplace discipline on organizational performance at Sappi Saiccor, Umkomaas. Descriptive and exploratory research was adopted. The mixed methods approach was used to collect data with stratified and purposive sampling techniques to select 291 participants from a population of approximately 1200 Sappi Saiccor, Umkomaas employees in KwaZulu Natal. Also, an online questionnaire and structured interview grid were used to collect the data with the application of SPSS (version 27.0) and NVivo (version 12.0). The result of the study shows a positive relationship between workplace discipline and the impact of COVID-19.

Ferine *et al.* (2022) looked at the effects of organizational culture and training and development on work discipline and performance. The data for the study was directly obtained from employees of a municipal water corporation in Medan, Indonesia, with a total of 204 participants. Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed in carrying out the analysis. The

results revealed that organizational culture and training and development positively and significantly affect performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

A descriptive survey research design is employed for this study. The population is made up of core and non-core staff of Access bank, Eco bank, First Bank of Nigeria Limited, Heritage bank, Polaris bank and Wema bank located in Ondo town, Ondo State. The total population of the study is two hundred and thirty-three (233) from the deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. This study adopted Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size computation. The Krejcie and Morgan sample size calculation is based on $p = 0.05$ where the probability of committing type I error is less than 5% or $p < 0.05$

$$S = X^2NP(1 - P) / d^2(N - 1) + X^2P(1 - P)$$

From the sample, size formula given above the Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the sample size for this study is as computed below:

$$S = \frac{X^2NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + X^2P(1 - P)}$$

$$S = \frac{447.5464(0.5)}{0.58 + 0.9604}$$

$$S = \frac{223.7732}{1.5404}$$

$$S = 145$$

Stratified random (probability) sampling technique was carried out in selecting the 145 respondents from the total staff of 233 of both core and non-core staff of the different deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. Primary data were engaged for this study, questionnaires were used to collect the data.

Reliability of Instrument

In this study, the Alpha Cronbach test was employed to ascertain the reliability of the study instrument and the result is presented below:

Table 3.1: Test for Reliability

Item	Obs	Sign	item-test correlation	item-rest correlation	average interitem covariance	alpha
op	134	+	0.8079	0.6165	.0533656	0.3556
dp	134	+	0.2407	0.0320	.1628676	0.6449
da	134	+	0.6942	0.4599	.0819556	0.4657
dpo	134	+	0.6551	0.3703	.0913976	0.5158
dc	134	-	0.5774	0.2438	.11296	0.5951
Test scale					.1005093	0.5864

Source: Author Compilation from STATA 14

The table above shows the Cronbach Alpha test for reliability, consistency and validity of the study instrument which is the questionnaire. The minimum acceptable value for Cronbach's alpha is 0.50; Below this value the internal consistency of the common range is low. Meanwhile, the maximum expected value is 0.90; Above this value is perceived as redundancy or duplication. Alpha values between 0.55 and 0.90 are usually preferred. In this study, the Cronbach Alpha test results as seen from the table above show a value of 0.58 which makes the instrument for this study reliable and valid.

Model of Specification

In evaluating employee discipline management and organization of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. The ordinary Least Square Regression Model was used to attain the coefficient of the variables. Four variables were used to represent the independent variables which are disciplinary procedures, disciplinary actions, disciplinary policies and disciplinary codes. While the dependent variable is organizational performance. The model for the study is functionally stated below:

$$OP' = (DP, DA, DPO, DC)' \dots\dots\dots(3.1)$$

The model is econometrically stated as:

$$OP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DP_i + \beta_2 DA_i + \beta_3 DPO_i + \beta_4 DC_i + \epsilon_i \dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

Where:

- OP = Organizational Performance
- DP = Disciplinary Procedures
- DA = Disciplinary Actions
- DPO = Disciplinary Policies
- DC = Disciplinary Codes
- β_0 = intercept
- $\beta_1 - \beta_4 > 0$ = Coefficient of DP, DA, DPO and DC
- ϵ_i = Error term
- i = Samples of deposit money banks in Ondo town

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Normality Test

Particularly, when testing for normality, where the probabilities > 0.05, it indicates that the data are NORMAL. Conversely, where the probabilities < 0.05, it indicates that the data are NOT NORMAL.

Table 4.1: Test of Data Normality

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
op	134	0.97531	3.118	2.591	0.00478
dp	134	0.96822	4.013	3.166	0.00077
da	134	0.96565	4.338	3.343	0.00041
dpo	134	0.99222	0.983	-0.040	0.51585
dc	134	0.98930	1.352	0.686	0.24625

Source: Author (2023)

Table 4.1 shows the result obtained from the Shapiro-Wilk normality test for the data employed in this study. It is observed that the dependent variable of organizational performance ($Z=2.591$; $\text{Prob}>Z=0.00478$) is not normally distributed since the probability of the z-statistic is significant at 5% level. In the case of the independent variables, the table shows that disciplinary procedure ($Z=3.166$; $\text{Prob}>Z=0.00077$) and disciplinary actions ($Z=3.343$; $\text{Prob}>Z=0.00041$) are not normally distributed since the probabilities of the z-statistics are significant at 5% level. However, disciplinary policies ($Z=-0.040$; $\text{Prob}>Z=0.51585$) and disciplinary codes ($Z=0.686$; $\text{Prob}>Z=0.24625$) follows a normal distribution since the probability of the z-statistic is insignificant at 1% or 5% level. The interpretation of the data normally test is in line with the studies of Jarque and Bera (1987).

Correlation Analysis

In this study, the Spearman rank correlation is employed since the data employed does not come from a normal distribution. The result obtain from the Spearman correlation is presented.

Table 4.2: Correlation Analysis

	op	dp	da	dpo	dc
op	1.0000				
dp	0.0236	1.0000			
da	0.6121	-0.0406	1.0000		
dpo	0.4942	0.0327	0.3075	1.0000	
dc	-0.2928	-0.0270	-0.2190	-0.1011	1.0000

Author’s computation (2023)

In the case of the correlation between disciplinary management and organizational performance the above results show that there exists a positive association between disciplinary procedures and organizational performance (0.0236). There is a positive association between disciplinary actions and organizational performance (0.6121). There is also a positive association between disciplinary policies and organizational performance (0.4942). Finally, the study shows that there is a negative and moderate association between disciplinary codes and organizational performance (-0.2928). However, to test our hypotheses a regression results will be needed since correlation test does not capture cause-effect relationship.

Regression Analyses

In order to examine the cause-effect relationships between the dependent variables and independent variables as well as to test the formulated hypotheses, the study relied on a pool OLS regression analysis. The OLS regression results obtained is presented and discussed below.

Table 4.3: Regression Result

op	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
dp	.0267655	.096524	0.28	0.782	-.1638599	.2173909
da	.4921543	.0670186	7.34	0.000	.3597992	.6245094
dpo	.3056984	.059933	5.10	0.000	.1873366	.4240602
dc	-.1537485	.0552841	-2.78	0.006	-.2629292	-.0445678
_cons	1.493323	.4851327	3.08	0.002	.5352338	2.451412

F-Statistics: {34.10 (0.0000)}; R-Squared: 0.4602; Mean VIF: 1.08; Hetttest: {3.45 (0.0633)}

Table 4.3 represents the result obtained from the regression analysis for this study. From the table it is observed from the pool OLS regression that the R-squared value of 0.4602 shows that about 46% of the systematic variations in organizational performance as the dependent variable of the study was jointly explained by the independent variables in the model. This implies that about 54% of the changes in organizational performance as the dependent variable could not be explained by the variables. The unexplained part of organizational performance can be attributed to the exclusion of other independent variables that can affect organizational performance as the dependent variable but were captured in the error term. Furthermore, the F-statistic value of 34.10 and the associated p-value of 0.0000 shows that the specified model on the overall is statistically significant at 1% level. This means that the regression model is valid and can be used for statistical inference. However, the study conducts some post regression test to further ascertain the validity of the pool OLS regression. These tests include multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity.

Test of Hypotheses

In this study, the hypotheses are tested using the result of the OLS regression in table 7.

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant impact of disciplinary procedures on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State.*

The results obtained from the OLS regression model revealed that disciplinary procedures [coef. = 0.027 (0.782)] has a statistically insignificant impact on organizational performance of deposit

money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State at neither 5% nor 1% significant level. The result implies that the disciplinary procedures have a positive statistically insignificant impact on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. Hence, the null hypotheses that there is no significant impact of disciplinary procedures on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant impact of disciplinary procedures on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State during the period under review.

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant influence of disciplinary actions on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State.*

The results obtained from the OLS regression model revealed that disciplinary actions [coef. = 0.492 (0.000)] has a statistically significant influence on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State at 1% significant level. The result implies that the disciplinary actions have a positive statistically significant influence on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. Hence, the null hypotheses that there is no significant impact of disciplinary actions on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of disciplinary actions on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State during the period under review.

Hypothesis 3: *There is no significant impact of disciplinary policies on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State.*

The results obtained from the OLS regression model revealed that disciplinary policies [coef. = 0.306 (0.000)] has a statistically significant impact on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State at 1% significant level. The result implies that the disciplinary policies have a positive statistically significant impact on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. Hence, the null hypotheses that there is no significant impact of disciplinary policies on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant impact of disciplinary policies on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State during the period under review.

Hypothesis 4: *There is no significant influence of disciplinary codes on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State.*

The results obtained from the OLS regression model revealed that disciplinary codes [coef. = -0.154 (0.006)] has a statistically significant influence on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State at 5% significant level. The result implies that the disciplinary codes have a negative statistically significant influence on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of disciplinary codes on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant impact of disciplinary codes on the organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo State during the period under review.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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In conclusion disciplinary actions and disciplinary policies significantly improves organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state during the period under review. However, disciplinary codes significantly reduce organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state during the period under review. Finally, it was concluded that disciplinary procedures have no significant effect on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Ondo town, Ondo state.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study, we carefully recommend as follows that:

- i. Organizations especially DMBs should incorporate disciplinary procedure aims to promote fairness and procedural justice in dealing with employee discipline.
- ii. Disciplinary actions should be taken when employees err after repeated warnings.
- iii. Disciplinary policy and action must be shaped with labour and management in agreement since the employees of today are better than the employee of yesterday and the existence of trade unionism gives today's employee more or better privileges and opportunities than the employee of yesterday.
- iv. Institutionalization of disciplinary codes. Disciplinary codes are reflective of a collective agreement between the employer and trade unions and it is to be implemented by management to improve employees' conduct and performance within a collective bargaining framework.

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